

Research Article

Nomenclatural novelties in Acanthaceae and a new species of *Justicia* from Madagascar

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Article Details: Received: 2025-01-06 | Accepted: 2025-03-26 | Available online: 2025-03-27

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Abstract: A new species *Justicia benoistii* from Madagascar is described here by providing a direct reference to the description of invalid species name *Duvernoia curviflora* Benoist. Two new combinations *Isoglossa lancifolia* (Ridl.) R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar and *Justicia roseana* (Leonard) R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar are proposed here for *Leda lancifolia* Ridl. and *Jacobinia roseana* Leonard respectively. In addition, a new name *Justicia lallanii* R.Kr.Singh is proposed here for *J. lancifolia* (Nees) V.M.Badillo, being a later homonym of *J. lancifolia* (Ridl.) Ridl. ex S.Moore.

Keywords: *Amphiscopia lancifolia*, *Duvernoia curviflora*, Endemic, *Isoglossa*, *Jacobinia roseana*, *Justicia lancifolia*, *Leda lancifolia*, Madagascar, Malaysia, Mexico, Peru

Introduction

In current circumscription, *Amphiscopia* Nees, *Duvernoia* Nees and *Jacobinia* Moric. are synonymous to the genus *Justicia* L., and *Leda* C.B.Clarke is synonymous to the genus *Isoglossa* Oerst. (Manzitto-Tripp et al., 2022). The species name *Duvernoia curviflora* described by Benoist (1964) is invalid because in the protologue he cited two gatherings as types (*H. Humbert*, *L. Bégue* & *R. Capuron 29582* and *Randriamiera 6391*). The citation of types by Benoist is contrary to Article 40.2 Ex. 1 of Shenzhen Code (Turland et al., 2018). To accommodate and validate the invalid species name *Duvernoia curviflora* Benoist under the genus *Justicia*, a new species *Justicia benoistii* R.Kr.Singh is described here in accordance to Article 38.13. of Shenzhen Code (Turland et al., 2018) by providing a direct reference to the description of *Duvernoia curviflora* Benoist (1964). Two new combinations *Isoglossa*

lancifolia (Ridl.) R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar and *Justicia roseana* (Leonard) R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar are made for *Leda lancifolia* Ridl. and *Jacobinia roseana* Leonard respectively. Further, a new name *Justicia lallanii* R.Kr.Singh is proposed here for illegitimate name *J. lancifolia* (Nees) V.M.Badillo, being a later homonym of *J. lancifolia* (Ridl.) Ridl. ex S.Moore.

Nomenclature

Isoglossa lancifolia (Ridl.) R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar, *comb. nov.*

Leda lancifolia Ridl., J. Linn. Soc., Bot. 41: 295. 1913. *Justicia lancifolia* (Ridl.) Ridl. ex S.Moore, J. Bot. 60: 358. 1922.

Holotype: Malaysia, Me Muang Gasing, Ulu Langat, Selangor, February 1912, C.B. Kloss s.n. (K000884186!, Figure 1).

Distribution: Endemic to Malaysia.

Justicia benoistii R.Kr.Singh, *sp. nov.*

Duvernoia curviflora Benoist, Bull. Soc. Bot. France 111: 428. 1964, *nom. inval.* [contrary to Article 40.2 Ex. 1 of Shenzhen Code (Turland et al., 2018)].

Holotype: Madagascar, Forêt de Zombitsy (Sakaraha), aux confins des bassins du Fiherenana et de l'Onilahy, Forêt tropophile sur sables siliceux de l'Isalo, 600–850 m, March 1955, H. Humbert, L. Bégue & R. Capuron 29582 (P00137128!, Figure 2).

Paratypes: Madagascar, Soalala, RN 8, 6 May 1954, *Randriamiera* 6391 (P00137129!, Figure 3 and K000419187!, Figure 4).

Distribution: Endemic to Madagascar.

Etymology: Named after Raymond Benoist (1881-1970), French Botanist.

Notes: While describing *Duvernoia curviflora*, Benoist (1964) cited the type information as “Forêt de Zombitsy (Sakaraha), aux confins des bassins du Fiherenana et de l'Onilahy, forêt tropophile sur sables siliceux de l'Isalo, alt. 600-850 mètres, HUMBERT, BÉGUÉ & CAPURON 29582; district de Soalala RANDRIAMIERA 6391”. The type citation given by Benoist is contrary to Article 40.2 Ex. 1 of Shenzhen Code (Turland et al., 2018) because he cited two gatherings as types (*H. Humbert, L. Bégue & R. Capuron 29582* and *Randriamiera 6391*). Thus, the species name *Duvernoia curviflora* Benoist is invalid. However, *Duvernoia* Nees is synonymous to the genus *Justicia* L. and therefore, a new species *Justicia benoistii* R.Kr.Singh is described here in accordance to Article 38.13. of Shenzhen Code (Turland et al., 2018) by providing a direct reference to the description given by Benoist (1964: 428).

Justicia lallanii R.Kr.Singh, *nom. nov.*

Amphiscopia lancifolia Nees, Prodr. [A. P. de Candolle] 11: 357. 1847. *Ecbolium lancifolium* (Nees)

Figure 1: Holotype of *Leda lancifolia* Ridl. (K000884186, © The Trustees of the Royal Botanic Gardens, Kew)

Figure 2: Holotype of *Justicia benoistii* R.Kr.Singh (P00137128, © Muséum National d'Histoire Naturelle, Paris)

Figure 3: Paratype of *Justicia benoistii* R.Kr.Singh (P00137129, © Muséum National d'Histoire Naturelle, Paris)

Figure 4: Paratype of *Justicia benoistii* R.Kr.Singh (K000419187, © The Trustees of the Royal Botanic Gardens, Kew)

Figure 5: Isotype of *Amphiscopia lancifolia* Nees (MA00815523, © Herbarium of Real Jardín Botánico, Madrid)

Figure 6: Isotype of *Amphiscopia lancifolia* Nees (MA00815524, © Herbarium of Real Jardín Botánico, Madrid)

Figure 7: Image of holotype specimen of *Amphiscopia lancifolia* Nees (© Herbarium of Field Museum of Natural History, Chicago)

Figure 8: Holotype of *Jacobinia roseana* Leonard (US00137208, © National Museum of Natural History, Smithsonian Institution, Washington, D.C.)

Figure 9: Isotype of *Jacobinia roseana* Leonard (K000064728, © The Trustees of the Royal Botanic Gardens, Kew)

Kuntze, Revis. Gen. Pl. 2: 980. 1891. *Justicia lancifolia* (Nees) V.M.Badillo, Cat. Fl. Venez. [Pittier] 2: 419. 1947, *nom. illeg., non* (Ridl.) Ridl. ex S.Moore, J. Bot. 60: 358. 1922.

Holotype: Peru, *s.d.*, Ruiz *s.n.* (B, specimen not extant); isotype GZU000259675!, MA00815523! (Figure 5), MA00815524! (Figure 6).

Distribution: Endemic to Peru.

Etymology: Named after Shri Lallan Singh, father of the lead author.

Notes: Presently, holotype specimen of *Amphiscopia lancifolia* Nees is not extant at B herbarium, but its image is housed at F herbarium (Figure 7).

Justicia roseana (Leonard) R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar, *comb. nov.*

Jacobinia roseana Leonard, J. Wash. Acad. Sci. 32: 342. 1942.

Holotype: Mexico, Colima, Manzanillo, December 1890, *E. Palmer 946* (US00137208!, Figure 8); isotype K000064728! (Figure 9).

Distribution: Endemic to Mexico.

Acknowledgements

The lead author is thankful to the Director, Botanical Survey of India, Kolkata and Head of Office, Botanical Survey of India, Arid Zone Regional Centre, Jodhpur for facilities. Authors are grateful to the curators of the GZU, F, K, MA, P and US herbaria for the images and information of type specimens.

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